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Apprenticeship Education vs. School-based Vocational Programmes in the Swedish Upper Secondary School – different paths to the same goal?

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Abstract

Apprenticeship education is formally a part of the Swedish upper secondary school VET. Half of the time in apprenticeship education is workplace-based, compared to a minimum of approximately 12,5 percent in the regular VET-programmes. However, the apprenticeship education follows the same curriculum as the school-based VET. This way of organizing the apprenticeship education seems to build upon a failure to recognize differences in ways of knowing, such as *knowing that* and *knowing how*, or that the situated character of learning in two different practices, school and workplaces, probably will lead to development of different aspects of vocational knowing. The purpose of this article is to explore differences in the vocational knowing afforded in the Swedish apprenticeship education compared to school-based VET in the Child and recreation programme.

Keywords

apprenticeship education; school-based VET; vocational knowing; Child and Recreation Programme

1 Introduction

Since 2011, apprenticeship education is part of Swedish upper secondary school's vocational education. An explicit purpose of the apprenticeship education is to offer an alternative for both students and employers to the regular VET programmes by providing ample opportunities to develop vocational knowing "in practice". A difference between the regular VET programmes and the apprenticeship education is that students in apprenticeship education spend more than half of their educational time at one or several workplaces, compared to approximately 12,5 percent of workplace-based training in the regular VET-programmes.

However, a potential hindrance for the apprenticeship education is that the curriculum is the same as for the school-based VET. Thus, apprenticeship education is subordinated to school-based education, and instead of offering an alternative pathway there is a risk that the apprenticeship education becomes a form of work-based school education (Berglund & Lindberg 2012, Berglund et al. 2017).

This way of organizing the apprenticeship education seems to build upon a notion that *reading about* leads to the development of the same vocational knowing as *learning-in-practice*, i.e. there is a failure to recognize different dimensions of knowing, such as *knowing that* and *knowing how* (Ryle 1949), as well as a failure to recognize how activities at school and workplaces form different practices with different goals (cf. Lave & Wenger 1991). As a

consequence, the aforementioned subordination in relation to regular VET is framing how apprenticeship education is understood. This means for instance that vocational theory is seen as foreshadowing vocational practice, which in its' turn is perceived as applied theory (Carlgren 2015, 2017). In addition, there also seems to be a common belief that apprenticeship education is particularly suitable for "practically minded" persons (Berglund 2009, Berglund & Henning Loeb 2013, c.f. CEDEFOP 2017 of attitudes in Sweden to VET education), who learn by doing and not by thinking or reading – as if thinking or reading were not embedded within the “doings” of vocational tasks (cf. Karlsson 2006, Schön 1983).

In this paper, we will explore differences in vocational knowing afforded in school and work tasks in the apprenticeship education compared to the school-based VET in the Child and recreation programme in Swedish upper secondary school.

2 Theoretical framework

In vocational activities, knowing is embedded in various actions (Schön 1986). To "learn in practice" means that the students are provided opportunities to develop vocational knowing by gradually expanding their ability to participate in workplace-specific actions and thereby becoming increasingly more experienced and capable in participating in the workplace practices (Lave & Wenger 1991). A large part of vocational knowing is tacit (Polanyi 2013). By contrast, at school, students become more capable in participating in the school practice and develop vocational knowing in relation to what is afforded in and by the tasks in school, whether they are school tasks, vocational tasks or simulated tasks (Carlgren 2015, Lindberg 2003). Traditionally school knowing is to a higher degree acknowledging propositional knowing, i.e. knowing-that, rather than knowing how (Ryle 1949). For instance, the complexities of vocational knowing developed during workplace-based learning is often reduced to propositional knowing when written school tasks of the work-based education are assessed on the basis of written school tasks (Wyszynska Johansson 2015).

3 Methods

The Child and recreation (CR) programme orientated towards pedagogical work is investigated in this paper. School and work tasks that the students participate in and how these are described by participants is explored. The data comes from two small-scale case studies of ethnographic character, one of which is still ongoing. Both studies are financed by the Swedish National Agency for Education.

All participating students are in their second year of the three-year education. In the first study, vocational knowing in workplace-based learning in three different VET-programmes in the apprenticeship education was explored (Gåfväls & Paul forthcoming). The material from the CR programme consists of observations and films following an apprenticeship-student during two days at her workplace, as well as interviews with the supervisor, the VET-teacher and the student using film elicitation (El Guindi 2004). The second study is ongoing, with the aim of comparing vocational knowing developed at school-based VET and apprenticeship education in two different VET-programmes. The data for this paper consists of participatory observation at school and during the workplace-based part of the education in the CR programme. Semi-structured interviews with students, teachers and supervisors have also been conducted.

Figure 1 Data production.

4 Findings

In both the school-based VET and the apprenticeship education students, teachers and supervisors describe a perceived division between theory and practice in relation to school tasks vs. work tasks. School tasks were by the students talked about as “theory” and associated with characteristics such as “sit and listen”, “reading in books”, “writing”. Teachers and supervisors portrayed school tasks as promoting reflection and deeper understanding. Work tasks were described as “doings” by the students, and associated with for instance “experiencing”, “interaction [with children]” and “taking responsibility”. Sara, an apprenticeship-student, explains: “Here [at the workplace] we don’t talk about children’s development and such. [...] But I can see it here in another way than by reading in a school book.” The teachers and supervisors talked about participating in work tasks as giving access to experiences by which the students could develop “a gaze”, know-how and become more autonomous.

Differences between the two forms of education were mainly found in assigned school tasks during the work-based learning part. The school tasks for the school-based VET students are introduced during school weeks by lectures on a topic in a specific course. In relation to the work-based training the students are asked to collect information on a topic at their workplaces, which is then to be written about in a report. The written report is formed as a typical school text and it is central for assessment of the workplace-based part. The teachers in the school-based VET emphasized recurrently the academic basis of CR programme and the goal of providing the students with a good basis for future academic studies.

Figure 2 School practices foreshadowing how child security as a vocational knowing is assessed in school-based VET.

The figure (2) above, illustrates how in the school-based VET school tasks focusing on propositional knowing foregrounds practical knowing, but also how the vocational gaze and vocational judgment that might be develop in practice in regards to child safety, is to be presented in an academic form. In conversations with students it became evident that without this particular of observing child-safety the topic would not have come up at their workplaces.

The apprenticeship-students also have school tasks in relation to their work-based education. Their assignments typically involve planning activities for the children within a specific area, for instance physical movement for children. They have to write a plan, lead the activity with a group of children at the workplace, and then write an evaluation and a reflection about it. The planning of the activity is to be conducted in relation to the pre-school curriculum. These plans and evaluations resemble the kind of pedagogical planning that are common texts in pre-schools. The apprenticeship-students explain that their supervisors can ask about their school tasks and that they together plan how they are to be executed. But some aspects were seldom or never discussed with the supervisors, such as how to link the activity to the pre-school curriculum.

In the observations of the apprenticeship-students at their respective workplaces the tacit dimensions of central vocational knowing that otherwise was difficult to verbalize became more apparent (cf. Gåfvels & Paul forthcoming). One example is when an apprenticeship-student, Elsa, was in the hallway, helping a child to undress his outerwear. In the film, Elsa takes off the child's warm sweater, talking in a kind voice to him about the color of his sweater, before putting it on the shelf and helping the child into the pre-school groups unit. In the film-elicitation the teacher pointed out that Elsa should not have undressed the child, but rather supported the child in undressing by himself. She stressed how they at school on many occasions have talked about the significance of supporting children in becoming more independent in their day-to-day lives. The supervisor, on the other hand, focused on the hallway as a stressful space where the apprenticeship-student needs to "have a feeling and be able to read how much one should help and how much time and space is there for one to stay in the hallway. Of course, the children should undress themselves but you have to see when it is a training-situation, and what is not a training-situation." The supervisor described the hallway like a hub where the flow of children in (or out) should go as quickly as possible due to time-

constraints depending on the pre-school schedule and the other groups wanting to use the hallway. In the film-elicitation of the hallway situation knowing how to support the child in becoming more independent, how to communicate with the child and being able to “see” and “read” the current situation as well as the child and his/her needs and the flow of the whole pre-school and colleagues, were emphasized. Also, knowing what to prioritize was highlighted. These aspects of vocational knowing recurred also in other observed situations, and are termed as *day-to-day knowing*, *communicative knowing*, *vocational gaze* and *vocational judgement*. Of these the teacher and supervisor stressed that the two latter take the longest time to develop, but are crucial for becoming capable and independent.

Figure 3 Some crucial aspects of vocational knowing at the pre-school

From the whole body of data vocational gaze involves three aspects: being able to interpret i) a situation in relation to the entire pre-schools activities, ii) a complete situation and iii) an individual’s needs. The first one requires being conscious about worktimes, the flow in the entire pre-school and the schedule which in its turn is connected to time and take this in to consideration in one’s actions. The second aspect deals with being attentive to the surrounding and any needs arisen nearby. The third involves seeing different needs such as other staff-members or children’s needs. Vocational judgment is closely tied to vocational gaze and embedded within the other categories. It involves capability to decide in a qualified way what to do, when and how, such as being able to judge if being in the hallway with the child was a learning situation for the child or not.

5 Conclusions

There are several similarities in the two different educational paths and both set of students participate in school practice and workplace practices, and are thus provided opportunities to develop the knowing afforded in respective community of practice (Lave & Wenger 1991). At the workplaces, the vocational knowing involved developing a vocational gaze (Gåfväls 2016), which is tied to vocational judgement, whereas focus in school was mainly on propositional knowing. In this small-scale case study, it is not possible to draw broader conclusions on differences in vocational knowing developed in apprenticeship education vs. school-based VET. But one difference that has been identified involves the school tasks that students are assigned to do while at the workplace. As in previous research of CR programme workplace-based learning in the school-based VET was assessed mainly through the academic form of writing a report and not based on (talk about) the students’ actions at the workplaces or observations at the workplaces (Wyszynska Johansson 2015). The school tasks in the school-based VET had more significance for school educational practices than bearing vocational significance, i.e. showcasing possible academic drift (cf. Edwards & Miller 2008). The school-tasks in the apprenticeship education in turn resembled text genres possible to find at pre-schools, as well as involving typical work tasks such as leading different events for the children.

It can be questioned if Swedish apprenticeship education is an *alternative* way of developing vocational knowing compared to traditional Swedish school-based VET. Swedish

apprenticeship education can be considered a work-based school education (Berglund & Lindberg 2012, Berglund et al. 2017).

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